

Optimal Siting of Electric Vehicle Charging Stations, Wind Turbine Generators, and Battery Energy Storage System in an Enhanced IEEE 33-Bus Test System

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Received, 11 August 2025; Accepted, 22 December 2025; Published, 26 January 2026

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Abstract

Environmental concerns over fossil fuels and greenhouse gas emissions from transportation are driving interest in electric vehicles (EVs). However, EV integration poses challenges to the power grid, including voltage violations and power losses. This study optimizes the placement of electric vehicle charging stations (EVCS), wind turbine distributed generation (WTDG), and battery energy storage systems (BESS) in the IEEE 33-bus system using differential evolution (DE) algorithm. MATLAB was used for the optimization process, while OpenDSS handled the power flow analysis. Results show that increasing EVCS sites raises power losses, while integrating WTDGs and BESS improves performance by reducing the losses and improving the voltage profile. This study provides insights for optimizing EVCS allocation and renewable energy integration to promote sustainable transportation.

Keywords: Electric vehicle integration, battery energy storage system, differential evolution algorithm, MATLAB, OpenDSS, wind turbine distributed generation

Introduction

The heavy reliance on fossil fuels has led to serious environmental impacts, with the transportation sector alone consuming 64.5% of global fuel (Hanif et al., 2019) and emitting around 1.5 billion tons of greenhouse gases annually (Vardanyan et al., 2024). As a cleaner alternative, electric vehicles (EVs) have gained global traction, driven by their ability to reduce local emissions and reliance on internal combustion engines. However, large-scale EV adoption poses challenges to power system operations due to the proliferation of EV charging stations (EVCS) on distribution feeders and the stochastic nature of EV charging, which can result to increased apparent power losses, voltage instability, and potential transformer overloading (Ahmed et al.,

2021; Yong et al., 2015; Tavakoli et al., 2020).

A promising approach to mitigate these challenges is the integration of distributed generation (DG) technologies and energy storage systems (ESS) into the grid. Wind turbine (WT) DGs are particularly suitable due to their zero-emission operation and the increasing reliability of wind energy conversion systems (Fernandes & Ferreira, 2015). Optimally sited wind DG units can decentralize power production, reduce feeder losses, and improve voltage profiles (Phan et al., 2024; Sharma et al., 2021). Although the intermittent nature of wind energy introduces supply fluctuations that may affect grid stability (Khunkitti et al., 2022), these variations can be addressed by battery energy storage systems (BESS) that store surplus energy during off-peak periods and discharge this during high demand,

thereby smoothing power flow and enhancing system reliability (Yuan et al., 2020; Khunkitti et al., 2022).

Extensive research has been conducted on either the optimal siting of EVCS or renewable DG units. Khunkitti et al. (2022) has optimized the location and size of BESS together with renewable DGs on both IEEE 33-bus and 69-bus test systems that minimize the cost of transmission loss, peak power, and voltage deviation. Similarly, Yuan et al. (2020) proposed a methodology for the optimal allocation and sizing of Li-ion BESS to minimize total system losses using a newly developed Coyote optimization algorithm. Also, Paliwal (2020) optimized the placement of renewable DGs and storage units in IEEE 33-bus system using probabilistic load flow while considering the impact of penetration and seasonal effect on system losses and voltage profile. However, these works did not consider the proliferation of EVs in the distribution system and, hence, did not touch on the optimal allocation of EVCS.

Several studies that have taken EVs into account used different approaches. Houssein et al. (2021) solved the optimal placement problem that minimizes the total EVCS cost using a novel gradient-based optimizer, which includes identifying the placement of slow and fast CS. Similarly, Zeb et al. (2020) optimized the combination of three different chargers in an EVCS to minimize installation cost, losses, and transformer loading, which was simulated on a real distribution network in Islamabad, Pakistan. Meanwhile, multi-objective functions were formulated by Sharma et al. (2021) to identify the optimal capacity estimation of DGs and appropriate location of EVCS that minimize power losses and voltage deviation of the network, and by Moradi et al. (2015) for optimal siting and sizing of CS and renewable DGs aimed at reducing power loss, improving voltage stability, and lessening EV charging costs.

While several studies have examined EVCS or DG placement independently, fewer have explored their combined integration with BESS in a unified optimization model. For instance, Pastor et al. (2023) proposed a methodology that optimally locates and dimensions a cluster containing an EVCS, renewable DGs, and BESS from the perspective of both the system operator

and EVCS investor. Another one proposed a multi-objective EVCS-BESS planning model that minimizes the integrated cost of EVCS and BESS, economic costs of system losses, and voltage fluctuations on IEEE 33-bus system with renewable DGs (Alizadeh et al., 2024). Both papers focused on photovoltaic (PV) DGs, but its intermittent nature was not taken into account in system modelling. Moreover, the time-dependent EV charging behavior was not considered as well.

This study aims to address the identified gaps by simultaneously optimizing the siting of EVCS, WTDGs, BESS in an enhanced IEEE 33-bus test system. The present study takes into account the intermittent nature of wind resource by utilizing a probability distribution function based on the available wind speed data. It also considers the time-based EV charging patterns for different customer types, namely: residential, commercial, and industrial. Lastly, it investigates the effect of different BESS charging/discharging schedules on system losses and voltage deviation, which has not been touched by previous works.

Specifically, the study sought to determine the following using the IEEE 33-bus test system: (1) identify the impacts of integrating EVCS in the distribution system, (2) investigate the effect of integrating an increasing number of optimal sites for WTDG to a distribution system with EVCS, and (3) analyze the effect of incorporating BESS with different charging schedules to a distribution system with EVCS and WTDGs. These objectives were evaluated in terms of power loss and voltage deviation. Three optimization scenarios corresponding to each specific objectives were simulated in MATLAB using differential evolution (DE) algorithm, and with power flow analysis conducted in OpenDSS. The enhanced IEEE 33-bus test system accounted for realistic residential, commercial, and industrial load variations. Technical constraints, wind generation characteristics, and BESS capacity and scheduling were also considered.

Methodology

Electric Load Data

Enhanced IEEE 33-Bus Test System

Operating at 12.66kV with a load of 3.715 MW and 2.3 MVAR, the enhanced IEEE 33-bus test system consists of 33 buses, 32 fixed lines, three switchable lines, four DGs, two reactive power compensators, and one substation at bus one (Dolatabadi et al., 2021). The switchable lines were left open, resulting in a radial system as shown in Figure 1. The slack bus or bus one was omitted from the buses to be considered for the optimal sites.

This study considered a realistic representation of hourly load demand variations which was adopted from the study of Chia-Hung Lin et al. (2008) and is shown in Figure 2. The residential, commercial, and industrial load patterns were determined through statistical analysis of the actual hourly power consumption of customers selected using a stratified sampling method for a load survey study. Figure 1 illustrates the load classification of the buses in the IEEE 33-bus test system.

Figure 1
Single-line diagram of the test system.

Note. The diagram is from Manzano & Lebosada, 2025.

Figure 2
Hourly load profile of three customer types.

Note. This figure is adopted from Chia-Hung Lin et al., 2008.

EV Charging Load Data

The EVCS charging load data was adopted from Sharma et al. (2021), which estimated EV charging session complexities using Monte Carlo simulation. It was assumed that EVs begin charging immediately upon arrival until fully charged. Charging behavior was modeled across three types of stations: residential, commercial, and industrial, as shown in Figure 3.

Wind Speed Data

The wind speed data that was used to calculate the power output of WTDGs was based from a year-long dataset of hourly wind speeds in Kern County, California, USA. This location was selected specifically for its consistently high wind speeds, being home to an actual wind farm.

Wind Turbine DG Model

There are numerous variables taken into consideration to effectively model a WTDG. The wind speed data, a fundamental factor, occurs at random speeds which can be subjected to data fitting through the Weibull distribution. The Weibull function is given by (1),

$$f(V) = \frac{\beta}{\eta^\beta} V^{\beta-1} e^{-\left(\frac{V}{\eta}\right)^\beta} \tag{1}$$

where $f(V)$ is the probability density function; β is the shape parameter, in which $\beta > 0$; η is the scale parameter, in which $\eta > 0$; and V is the wind speed (m/s), in which $V > 0$.

Once the corresponding shape and scale parameters were calculated, the wind speed data were fitted to the Weibull distribution. This was done through the use of MATLAB functions that are configured for this distribution type.

The WTDG model that was used in this study was based on the Hummer H25.0-100KW turbine generator with a 100-kW nominal power rating (Bauer & Matysik, 2025). The specifications of this WT are listed in Table 1.

Table 1
Specifications of the WTDG unit.

PARAMETERS	VALUES
Cut-in Speed (m/s)	2.5
Rated Speed (m/s)	10
Cut-out Speed (m/s)	20
Nominal Power Rating (kW)	100

Note. This table is from Bauer & Matysik, 2025.

Figure 3
EV charging load profile of three customer types

Note. This figure is adopted from Sharma et al., 2021.

The power output of the WT generator was calculated as a function of wind speed, which is expressed in (2),

$$P(v) = \begin{cases} 0, & v < v_c \text{ or } v > v_s \\ P_{rated} \left(\frac{v-v_c}{v_r-v_c} \right)^3, & v < v_r \\ P_{rated}, & v_r \leq v \leq v_s \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where $P(v)$ is the wind power curve (kW); P_{rated} is the nominal power rating of the WT generator; v_c is the cut-in speed (m/s); v_r is the rated speed (m/s); v_s is the cut-out speed (m/s); and v is the wind speed (m/s).

Adopted from the study of Narcise & Aguirre (2016), the constant lagging power factor model was considered in this study. It encompasses a reactive power, which is dependent on the active power output of the WTDG unit and is given by (3),

$$Q_{DG} = \pm P_{DG} \tan(\cos^{-1}0.95) \quad (3)$$

where Q_{DG} and P_{DG} are the reactive (kVAR) and active (kW) power, respectively.

EVCS Model

The EVCS in this study was assumed to be equipped with Tesla Supercharger. This charger stands out for its high charging power technology, delivering a power rating of 250 kW. With its proprietary DC fast-charging system, it allows users rapid charging of EVs, significantly reducing charging times compared to traditional charging methods (Bishla & Khosla, 2023).

BESS Model

The BESS model, based on Zhang et al. (2014), aimed to address the variability of large-scale wind farms, with the optimal capacity set at 30% of the WT system's rated output. The model did not consider state of charge, assuming constant power during both charging and discharging hours.

Test Cases

Four cases were considered in the study. Case 1 or the base case, simulated a 24-hour load profile. Case 2 assessed the impact of EVCS integration on power loss and voltage profile. Case 3 included both EVCS and WTDG, while Case 4 added BESS at the DG site to evaluate various charging schedules.

Test case 2 included three subcases, each with an increasing number of EVCS. To reflect the three customer types used in the study, EVCS integration was scaled in multiples of three. Due to simulation hardware limitations, a maximum of nine EVCS was implemented. The subcases are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2
Subcases for test case 2

SUBCASE NUMBER	INTEGRATED EVCS
2.1	3
2.2	6
2.3	9

Test case 3 included three subcases, each integrating nine EVCS along with varying numbers of WT DG sites. By maintaining a constant number of EVCS and varying the number of DG sites, the test case aimed to assess the effect of DG placement on power loss mitigation.

According to Hung et al. (2013), improper DG placement and excessive penetration can cause increased losses, feeder overload, and voltage issues. Paliwal (2020) noted that DG penetration beyond 20% offers diminishing returns, with optimal performance between 20% to 40%. Accordingly, the total WTDG capacity was fixed at 1400 kW or fourteen 100-kW WTDG units distributed evenly across sites. Subcases under test case 3 are summarized in Table 3.

Test case 4 extends test case 3 by evaluating the impact of integrating BESS at WTDG sites, using the same parameters. Following Zhang et al. (2014), BESS capacity was set at 30% of the WTDG's total power output per site. Subcases are summarized in Table 4.

Three BESS charging schedules were simulated for this test case: first is 12 hours of discharging followed by 12 hours of charging (12D-12C); second is 12 hours of charging followed

Table 3
Subcases for test case 3.

SUBCASE NUMBER	NO. OF EVCS	NO. OF OPTIMAL SITES	NO. OF WTDG UNITS PER SITE	WTDG TOTAL POWER PER SITE (kW)
3.1	9	2	7	700
3.2	9	7	2	200
3.3	9	14	1	100

Table 4
Subcases for test case 4.

SUB CASE NUMBER	SCHEDULE	NO. OF EVCS	NO. OF OPTIMAL SITES	NO. OF WTDG UNIT PER SITE	WTDG TOTAL POWER PER SITE (kW)	BESS RATED POWER PER SITE (kW)
4.1.1	12D-12C					
4.1.2	12C-12D	9	2	7	700	210
4.1.3	4D-4C-3X					
4.2.1	12D-12C					
4.2.2	12C-12D	9	7	2	200	60
4.2.3	4D-4C-3X					
4.3.1	12D-12C					
4.3.2	12C-12D	9	14	1	100	30
4.3.3	4D-4C-3X					

by 12 hours of discharging (12C-12D), and third is three 4-hour discharging and charging cycles (4D-4C-3X).

Objective Function

The objective function, defined in (4), addresses the impact of high EV penetration on grid stability and power quality. To minimize apparent power loss, this study aimed to identify the optimal sites for EVCS and WTDGs integrated with BESS.

$$F = \min \Sigma S_{loss} \tag{4}$$

where F is the objective function and S_{loss} is the apparent power loss of the system (kVA).

Constraint

The voltage constraint, adopted from Boonraksa et al. (2018) and expressed in (5), requires that all buses in the distribution system operate within $\pm 5\%$ of the nominal system voltage following renewable DG output adjustments. Accordingly, the minimum and maximum bus voltage limits were set to 0.95 and 1.05 per unit (p.u.), respectively.

$$V_{min} \leq V_i \leq V_{max} \quad i \in b_{num} \tag{5}$$

where V_i is the voltage of bus i ; V_{min} and V_{max} are the minimum and maximum allowable voltages of bus i , respectively; and b_{num} is the total bus number.

K-Means Clustering Algorithm

K-means clustering partitions a dataset into K clusters, each represented by a centroid that minimizes the within-cluster sum of squared deviations (Farhang, 2017). The algorithm iteratively assigns data points to the nearest centroid based on similarity and updates centroids until convergence is reached (Wang et al., 2011). Following the study of Tupper et al. (2017), this method was applied to cluster wind power output samples according to stochastic variability, enabling categorization and standardization of wind speed patterns. The silhouette coefficient, used to evaluate clustering quality and optimize parameters, indicated that two clusters were optimal for the wind speed data in this study.

Power Flow Analysis

To evaluate the impact of integrating EVCS, WTDGs, and BESS into the test distribution network, multiple 24-hour power flow simulations were conducted using time-series data. EV charging profiles based on Sharma et al. (2021), which is illustrated in Figure 3, represented the peak load of 65 electric vehicles across residential, commercial, and industrial stations.

The system's performance was evaluated based on both total network losses and voltage profiles. Total voltage deviations (TVD) were computed on an hourly basis using the method proposed by Shaw et al. (2014), as shown in (6) and (7):

$$TVD = \sum_{i=1}^n |V_i - 1| \quad (6)$$

$$TVD_{ave} = \frac{TVD_A + TVD_B + TVD_C}{3} \quad (7)$$

where V_i is the phase voltage at the i^{th} bus (p.u.); n is the total number of buses; TVD_A , TVD_B , and TVD_C represent the total voltage deviations for phases A, B, and C, respectively; and TVD_{ave} is the average TVD of the system.

For each test case, power losses which consist of real $\%P_{loss}$, reactive $\%Q_{loss}$, and apparent $\%S_{loss}$ components, were recorded hourly and aggregated over the simulation period. To quantify the impact of each system modification,

the percentage change in power losses between any two scenarios was computed using the following generalized formulations:

$$\%P_{loss} = \frac{P_{loss,2} - P_{loss,1}}{P_{loss,1}} \quad (8)$$

$$\%Q_{loss} = \frac{Q_{loss,2} - Q_{loss,1}}{Q_{loss,1}} \quad (9)$$

$$\%S_{loss} = \frac{S_{loss,2} - S_{loss,1}}{S_{loss,1}} \quad (10)$$

where subscript "1" denotes the baseline scenario, while subscript "2" refers to the modified system configuration.

Differential Evolution Algorithm

The DE algorithm was configured with a population size of 600, a crossover rate of 0.3, a mutation rate of 0.45, and 600 iterations. The crossover and mutation rates were adopted from Moradi et al. (2015), while the population size and iteration count were determined through preliminary test runs. These values were selected to accommodate the large number of EVCS and WTDGs with BESS considered for optimal siting. Convergence was consistently achieved within approximately 200 iterations, and identical optimal solutions were obtained from convergence to the final iteration, validating both the adequacy of the parameters used and their ability to ensure sufficient exploration of possible site combinations.

Implementation

Initially, the DE parameters were defined, which includes the mutation factor, crossover probability, population size, and number of iterations. A population size of 600 individuals was used throughout the simulations. Each individual represented a unique and randomized configuration of sites, where the nature of the EVCS, WTDGs, or BESS depended on the specific test case scenario.

For cases involving WTs, which are test cases 3 and 4, wind speed data were modeled using a

Weibull distribution to capture the stochastic nature of wind resource. From this distribution, 1,000 wind speed samples per hour were generated and grouped using k-means clustering to reflect realistic variations. The average of the cluster centroids was used to represent the wind speed for each hour in the power flow simulations.

In Case 4, additional complexity was introduced through the integration of BESS, which operated in either charging or discharging mode based on a predefined schedule. When charging, the BESS was modeled as a load; when discharging, it acted as a supplementary generator in tandem with the WTDGs.

Each individual underwent a 24-hour time-series power flow simulation in OpenDSS. In these simulations, EVCS were modeled as loads, WT as generators, and BESS as either loads or generators, depending on their state of operation. Hourly power losses and bus voltages were recorded. At the end of each simulation, the total power losses were summed and the bus voltages were averaged. These values were used to compute a fitness score for each individual using the objective function defined in (4) that prioritized power loss minimization.

Following the initial evaluation, the DE algorithm proceeded through its evolutionary process. Mutation was applied to create a donor vector by perturbing randomly selected individuals from the current population. This vector was then used in the crossover operation to generate a trial individual. The trial solution underwent the same 24-hour power flow analysis and fitness evaluation. In the selection step, the fitness of the trial individual was compared with that of the target individual, and the one with the better fitness value was retained in the next generation. This process of mutation, crossover, simulation, and selection was repeated iteratively until the defined number of generations was completed. The flowchart summarizing the general DE implementation is shown in Figure 4.

Results

The simulation results are divided into four sections. First, the power loss and voltage deviation of the test system before any additional infrastructure integration is presented. Second,

the optimal locations of EVCS, WTDG, and BESS as determined by the DE algorithm are revealed. Third and fourth, the power loss and voltage deviation across the test cases, respectively, were compared with each other.

Base Case Simulation

The base case provided an initial assessment of the IEEE 33-bus test system under commercial, residential, and industrial load profiles. Over a 24-hour period, the total real, reactive, and apparent system losses were 1393.3940 kW, 849.4172 kVAR, and 1631.8873 kVA, respectively. Phase voltage discrepancies confirmed system imbalance. Additionally, voltage magnitudes decreased with increasing distance from the slack bus, with an average TVD of 0.0419 p.u. across all phases.

Optimal Sites

Three test cases were simulated on top of the base case to determine the effect of integrating additional elements into the power system. The optimal location of these elements that will minimize the losses in the test system as given by (4) was determined using the DE algorithm. The identified optimal location and the corresponding fitness values for each test case and their subcases are presented in Tables 5 to 7. For easier reference, the bus numbers are color-coded using the same color scheme in Figures 1 to 3.

Table 5
Optimal sites for case 2

SUBCASE	LOWEST FITNESS VALUE (kVA)	EVCS SITES
2.1	1656.95	2, 3, 19
2.2	1721.18	2, 3, 4, 19, 20, 22
2.3	1842.22	2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 19, 20, 21, 22

Figure 4
Flowchart of methodology implementation.

Table 6
Optimal sites for case 3

SUB CASE	LOWEST FITNESS VALUE (kVA)	EVCS SITES	WIND TURBINE DG SITES
3.1	1661.22	2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 19, 20, 21, 22	11, 13
3.2	1665.90	2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 19, 20, 21, 22	10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 29, 30
3.3	1667.98	2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 19, 20, 21, 22	8, 9, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 26, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33

Table 7
Optimal sites for case 4

SUB CASE	CHARGING SCHEDULE	FITNESS VALUE (kVA)	EVCS SITES	WIND TURBINE DG + BESS SITES
4.1.1	12D-12C	1708.73	2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 19, 20, 21, 22	8, 10
4.1.2	12C-12D	1674.10	2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 19, 20, 21, 22	12, 29
4.1.3	4D-4C-3X	1680.49	2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 19, 20, 21, 22	11, 29
4.2.1	12D-12C	1711.74	2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 19, 20, 21, 22	8, 9, 10, 11, 13, 27, 30
4.2.2	12C-12D	1675.22	2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 19, 20, 21, 22	8, 9, 11, 13, 14, 26, 33
4.2.3	4D-4C-3X	1680.54	2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 19, 20, 21, 22	8, 10, 12, 13, 14, 29, 30
4.3.1	12D-12C	1717.45	2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 19, 20, 21, 22	8, 9, 11, 12, 13, 14, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31
4.3.2	12C-12D	1678.90	2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 19, 20, 21, 22	8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 26, 27, 28, 30, 31, 32, 33
4.3.3	4D-4C-3X	1684.84	2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 19, 20, 21, 22	8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 16, 25, 26, 28, 29, 30, 31

Power Losses

The resulting real, reactive, and apparent power losses of the test system after integrating the elements in each test cases and their corresponding subcases are provided in this section. Table 8 compares the losses between the base case and the subcases of test case 2. Meanwhile, Table 9 summarizes the results of test case 3 and illustrates the percent change in losses relative to subcase 2.3. Finally, Table

10 shows the different losses for various BESS charging schedules and the percent change in relation to the corresponding subcases in test case 3.

Voltage Profile

In assessing the system’s voltage performance, the average TVD was used as a key parameter. TVD quantifies the deviation of bus voltage magnitudes from the nominal value

Table 8
Power losses comparison for case 2

CASE	NO. OF EVCS	P_{LOSS} (kW)	ΔP_{LOSS} (%)	Q_{LOSS} (kVAR)	ΔQ_{LOSS} (%)	S_{LOSS} (kVA)	ΔS_{LOSS} (%)
1	-	1393.52	-	849.55	-	1631.12	-
2.1	3	1415.58	+ 1.58	861.17	+ 1.37	1656.95	+ 1.52
2.2	6	1469.15	+ 5.29	896.70	+ 5.42	1721.18	+ 5.32
2.3	9	1570.46	+ 11.95	963.03	+ 12.54	1842.22	+ 12.11

Table 9
Power losses comparison for case 3.

CASE	NO. OF EVCS	P_{LOSS} (kW)	ΔP_{LOSS} (%)	Q_{LOSS} (kVAR)	ΔQ_{LOSS} (%)	S_{LOSS} (kVA)	ΔS_{LOSS} (%)
2.3	-	1570.46	-	963.03	-	1842.22	-
3.1	2	1420.13	- 9.57	861.91	- 10.50	1661.22	- 9.83
3.2	7	1423.49	- 9.36	865.38	- 10.14	1665.90	- 9.57
3.3	14	1424.27	- 9.31	868.10	- 9.86	1667.98	- 9.46

Table 10
Power losses comparison for case 4.

CASE	CHARGING SCHEDULE	P_{LOSS} (kW)	ΔP_{LOSS} (%)	Q_{LOSS} (kVAR)	ΔQ_{LOSS} (%)	S_{LOSS} (kVA)	ΔS_{LOSS} (%)
3.1	-	1420.13	-	861.91	-	1661.22	-
4.1.1	12D-12C	1458.85	+ 2.73	889.67	+ 3.22	1708.73	+ 2.86
4.1.2	12C-12D	1429.74	+ 0.68	870.89	+ 1.04	1674.10	+ 0.78
4.1.3	4D-4C-3X	1434.52	+ 1.01	875.32	+ 1.56	1680.49	+ 1.16
3.2	-	1423.49	-	865.38	-	1665.90	-
4.2.1	12D-12C	1460.86	+ 2.63	892.15	+ 3.09	1711.74	+ 2.75
4.2.2	12C-12D	1430.35	+ 0.48	872.04	+ 0.77	1675.22	+ 0.56
4.2.3	4D-4C-3X	1435.00	+ 0.81	874.64	+ 1.07	1680.54	+ 0.88
3.3	-	1424.27	-	868.10	-	1667.98	-
4.3.1	12D-12C	1465.08	+ 2.87	896.19	+ 3.24	1717.45	+ 2.97
4.3.2	12C-12D	1433.10	+ 0.62	874.60	+ 0.75	1678.90	+ 0.65
4.3.3	4D-4C-3X	1438.17	+ 0.98	877.70	+ 1.10	1684.84	+ 1.01

of 1.0 p.u. across all buses and phases. A lower average TVD indicates that voltages remain closer to the nominal value, reflecting better voltage regulation and overall system stability. Figure 5 compares the TVD of the base case with that of the test case 2 subcases. In contrast,

Figure 6 juxtapose the TVD of subcase 2.3 with that of the test case 3 subcases. Finally, Figure 7 differentiates the TVD of the test case 4 subcases with the corresponding subcases of test case 3. It is worthwhile to note that only the cases under the BESS schedule of 12-hour charging

Figure 5
Average TVD of case 2 subcases.

Figure 6
Average TVD of case 3 subcases.

Figure 7
Average TVD of case 4 subcases under the 12C-12D BESS schedule.

followed by 12-hour discharging (12C-12D) were considered as these subcases showed the lowest losses as illustrated in Table 10.

Discussion

A consolidated evaluation of all test cases reveals distinct trends in optimal siting strategies depending on the components integrated. In Case 2, a greater number of EVCS sites was associated with higher total power losses, as shown in Table 5. Although more sites may enhance service availability, they also increase load stress and resistive losses in the network. Optimal sites were consistently located in commercial and industrial areas. As shown in Figure 2, these load types typically exhibit higher per-unit load profiles than residential loads during peak hours. Strategic placement near the substation at bus one further minimized the line losses by reducing transmission distance.

Meanwhile, Table 6 shows the optimal location of increasing number of WTDGs across three subcases. Subcase 3.1 yielded the lowest power loss, while subcase 3.3 recorded the highest. Despite variations in DG location, the EVCS sites remained consistent across all subcases and mirrored those in subcase 2.3 which are concentrated in commercial and industrial areas near the slack bus. WTDGs were initially clustered near commercial buses but expanded into residential areas as their number increased. This shift reflects the need to compensate for the residential demand where fewer generators were assigned. DGs were notably absent in industrial areas, likely due to the presence of nearby DGs as illustrated in Figure 1 and their proximity to the slack bus, which already ensured sufficient power delivery.

Case 4 evaluated the optimal siting of EVCS, WTDG, and BESS to minimize the total apparent power loss. BESS units were collocated with DGs, and three charging schedules were tested per subcase, which are summarized in Table 7. In all subcases, EVCS were consistently placed near the supply bus. These sites, which are the same as the ones identified in Case 3, helped minimize resistive losses through shorter feeder line distances. WTDGs with BESS were primarily sited in residential and commercial buses farther

from the supply bus, reflecting their role in supporting localized demand and compensating for load disparities across the network. Their locations varied across subcases due to differences in BESS charging behavior and wind power output. The integration of BESS introduced dynamic load-generation interactions, i.e., BESS operated as loads while charging, reducing the net power output of the DG-BESS system. This dual role influenced the optimization results and led to site variations not seen in previous cases. The consistent EVCS placement confirmed the stability of the optimization approach, while the shifting of DG-BESS locations demonstrated the system's adaptive response to variable renewable generation and storage conditions.

The real, reactive, and apparent power losses for the base case and Case 2 subcases are summarized in Table 8. These results underscore that EVCS integration acts as an additional load, causing increased generation output from the supply bus and generators. Accordingly, the increase in system load directly correlates with increased active and reactive power losses, leading to higher apparent losses.

In contrast, Case 3 demonstrated that incorporating wind turbine DGs significantly mitigates power losses when integrated with EVCS. As shown in Table 9, a higher number of optimal sites led to slightly higher power losses despite constant total DG capacity, suggesting that fewer sites with larger capacity are more effective in reducing system losses.

In Case 4, the integration of BESS at WTDG sites has led to a slight increase in overall power losses as illustrated in Table 10. While the BESS contributes to system support during its discharging phase, it simultaneously elevates the load demand during charging. Among the three tested charging schedules, the second mode consistently resulted in the lowest power losses. Although the differences in power losses across the schedules are marginal, the results indicate that the BESS charging strategy has a discernible impact on overall system losses.

The observed increase in power losses, ranging from 0.48% to 3.24%, can be primarily attributed to the fixed nature of the BESS charging schedule. The schedules being fixed lacked the adaptability to the temporal variability of wind generation, electrical demand, and EVCS loads. As a result,

the BESS occasionally discharges during periods of low demand, contributing unnecessary power to the system and leading to inefficiencies. The charging schedule is only optimal when it coincides with periods of sustained high wind availability and low generation requirements from the WTDGs. Consequently, the lack of dynamic coordination between the BESS operation and the system's fluctuating load profile contributes to its suboptimal performance in minimizing power losses.

It is also demonstrated that a higher number of optimal sites for WTDGs and BESS does not necessarily reduce apparent power losses. Similar in Case 3, some Case 4 subcases with fewer DG and BESS sites achieved better loss reduction. This is likely due to higher per-site capacity in fewer-site setups compared to the lower capacity of more distributed ones. Moreover, increased BESS deployment adds to cumulative charging demand during its charging state. Thus, while wider spatial distribution has benefits, it must be balanced with its impact on system load and efficiency.

With regards to the TVD, the integration of EVCS into the system resulted in reduced bus voltage levels compared to the base case. Despite strategic placement of EVCS, all Case 2 subcases exhibited higher average TVD values as illustrated in Figure 5. These elevated TVD values indicate greater voltage deviations at the buses, largely due to the increased power demand introduced by the EVCS integration.

A notable improvement in voltage profile was observed with the integration of WTDGs. Subcase 3.1 yielded bus voltages closest to the nominal 1.0 p.u. reference by having the lowest TVD as shown in Figure 6. This improvement is largely due to localized generation from wind DGs, which supports voltage levels at remote buses, supplemented by reactive power compensators that regulate voltage through reactive power control.

Further enhancement in voltage profile was achieved by incorporating BESS at the optimal sites of WTDGs. This integration led to lower average TVD values, as shown in Figure 7. Subcase 4.2.2 achieved bus voltages closest to the nominal reference of 1.0 p.u. The improved voltage regulation in Case 4 is attributed to the presence of BESS, which helps mitigate voltage

fluctuations by absorbing excess energy during periods of high generation and supplying power during low generation or high demand. This complementary operation with wind DGs ensures that bus voltages remain within acceptable operational limits.

Conclusion

This study optimized the integration of EVCS, WTDGs, and BESS in a modified IEEE 33-bus distribution system using DE algorithm. The goal was to minimize apparent power losses while evaluating impacts on voltage profile across various test cases.

Integrating EVCS alone resulted in increased power losses and degraded voltage profiles due to additional loads. Adding WTDGs significantly improved performance, with fewer high-capacity units proving more effective than numerous smaller ones. These DGs, optimally sited near EVCS and high-load areas, improved voltage support and reduced the average TVD.

The inclusion of BESS further enhanced voltage regulation and peak shaving, though their effectiveness depended on the charging schedule. The most favorable outcome occurred when BESS charged during low demand and discharged during peak periods.

Overall, optimal placement of WTDGs and appropriately scheduled BESS can mitigate the adverse effects of EVCS on distribution systems. TVD served as a useful metric for evaluating voltage performance. Future work should explore larger networks, improve EVCS and BESS modeling, incorporate hybrid renewable systems, and consider practical constraints like spatial limitations and unit specifications for DG deployment.

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